

ABRomics metadata referential

Sample	Strain	Sequencing
--------	--------	------------

ABRomics metadata specifications

Field name	Description/guidelines for ABRomics users	ABRomics status	Type	Accepted values / validation	Additional comments	Metadata type
Sample type	<i>Indicate if the sample is collected on human, on animal, in an environment or another source (other, eg, food). "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list "Sample type" in the Fields_values tab.</i>	mandatory	string	{human, animal, environment, other}	Metagenome and genome	S A M P L E
Host species	<i>Species of the host. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected" (if information is missing).</i>	mandatory	string	{Homo sapiens, Mus musculus, Gallus gallus, Bos taurus, Ovis aries, Anas platyrhynchos, Capra hircus, Sus domesticus, Equus caballus, Other, Not collected, Not applicable}	Metagenome and genome Animal	
Sample source (for human or animal)	<i>Site of isolation for samples collected on human or animal. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected" (if information is missing).</i>	mandatory	string	{Blood, Fluid, Fluid (Cerebrospinal (CSF)), Fluid (Pericardial), Fluid (Pleural), Fluid (Vaginal), Fluid (Amniotic), Saliva, Tissue, Anus, Duodenum, Eye, Intestine, Lower respiratory tract, Bronchus, Lung, Bronchiole, Alveolar sac, Pleural sac, Pleural cavity, Trachea, Rectum, Skin, Stomach, Upper respiratory tract, Anterior Nares, Esophagus, Ethmoid sinus, Nasal Cavity, Middle Nasal Turbinate, Inferior Nasal Turbinate, Nasopharynx (NP), Oropharynx (OP), Breast Milk, Feces, Mucus, Semen, Sputum, Sweat, Tear, Urine, Vagina, Cranial hair, Catheter, Bone and joint, Prosthesis, Dialysis, Surgical site, Urethra, Sinus, Not Collected}	Metagenome and genome	
Sample source (for environment)	<i>Site of isolation for samples collected in an environment. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate "Not collected" (if information is missing).</i>	mandatory	string	{River water, WWTP effluent, Farm effluent, Hospital effluent, Agricultural soil, Other, Not collected}	Metagenome and genome	
Sample country	<i>Name of the country in which the sample has been collected. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values or indicate either "Not collected" or "XX" (if information is missing).</i>	mandatory	string	Country english full name or ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 code, eg. FR for France, see the list in Field_values tab	Metagenome and genome	
Sample ZIP code	<i>ZIP code of the location where the sampling was performed.</i>	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
GPS latitude	<i>The latitude coordinates of the geographical location where the sampling was performed. "Accepted values / validation" column: must be specified as decimal degrees latitude in format "d[d.ddd]", eg, 38.98. Latitude must be between -90.0000 and 90.0000 degrees.</i>	optional	string	Specify as decimal degrees latitude in format "d[d.ddd]", eg, 38.98. Must be between -90.0000 and 90.0000 degrees	Metagenome and genome (mostly for environmental samples)	
GPS longitude	<i>The longitude coordinates of the geographical location where the sampling was performed. "Accepted values / validation" column: must be specified as decimal degrees longitude in format "d[dd.ddd]", eg, 77.11. Longitude must be between -180.0000 and 180.0000 degrees.</i>	optional	string	Specify as decimal degrees longitude in format "d[dd.ddd]", eg, 77.11. Must be between -180.0000 and 180.0000 degrees	Metagenome and genome (mostly for environmental samples)	
Sample date	<i>The date of sampling. "Accepted values / validation" column: must be in this format: "DD/MM/YYYY".</i>	mandatory	date	Must be in "DD/MM/YYYY" format	Metagenome and genome	
Original sample ID	<i>ID of the sample emitted by the sampling laboratory. "Accepted values / validation" column: Original sample ID value must be unique in the whole document.</i>	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	

ABRomics metadata referential

Sample	Strain	Sequencing
--------	--------	------------

ABRomics metadata specifications

Field name	Description/guidelines for ABRomics users	ABRomics status	Type	Accepted values / validation	Additional comments	Metadata type
Sample collected by	Name of the person or name of the institution that collected the sample.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Sample collector contact email	Contact email adress of the person/institution to contact.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Travel country	Countries where the host travelled to in the last 3 months prior to the sampling (list multiple countries with comma-separated values). "Accepted values / validation" column: choose from the list "Country list (alpha-2 code)" in the Fields_values tab.	optional	string	free text; Country 2-letters code, see the list in Field_values tab. Country english full name is not accepted . If multiple countries, separate each by comma	Metagenome and genome	
Sample comment	Any comments on the sample.	optional	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	
Microorganism scientific name	Scientific name of the isolated microorganism. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list of accepted values.	mandatory	string	{Escherichia coli, Shigella spp., Klebsiella pneumoniae, Klebsiella aerogenes, Enterobacter cloacae, Citrobacter freundii, Citrobacter koseri, Morganella morganii, Salmonella enterica, Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Acinetobacter baumannii, Enterococcus faecalis, Enterococcus faecium, Campylobacter jejuni, Campylobacter coli, Campylobacter fetus, Campylobacter lari, Campylobacter upsaliensis, Campylobacter ornithocola, Campylobacter armoricus, Aliarcobacter butzleri, Arcobacter cryaerophilus, Arcobacter skirrowii, Helicobacter pylori, Helicobacter pullorum, Helicobacter cinaedi, Arcobacter cibarius, Proteus mirabilis, Other}	Genome	S T R A I N
Microorganism subspecies	Name of the sub-species of the isolated microorganism.	optional	string	free text	Genome	
Strain ID (or name)	Name of the isolated strain. "Accepted values / validation" column: Strain ID (or name) value must be unique in the whole document .	mandatory	string	free text	Genome	
NCBI taxonomy ID	NCBI taxonomy ID of the isolated microorganism. "Accepted values / validation" column: NCBI taxonomy ID value must be superior to 0.	optional	integer	number higher than 0	Genome	
Instrument model	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment. "Accepted values / validation" column: choose one value from the list.	mandatory	string	{HiSeq X Five, HiSeq X Ten, Illumina HiScanSQ, Illumina HiSeq 1000, Illumina HiSeq 1500, Illumina, HiSeq 2000, Illumina HiSeq 2500, Illumina HiSeq 3000, Illumina HiSeq 4000, Illumina iSeq 100, Illumina MiSeq, Illumina MiniSeq, Illumina NovaSeq 6000, NextSeq 500, NextSeq 550, PacBio RS, PacBio RS II, Sequel, Ion Torrent PGM, Ion Torrent Proton, Ion Torrent S5, Ion Torrent S5 XL, MinION, GridION, PromethION, BGISEQ-500, DNBSEQ-T7, DNBSEQ-G400, DNBSEQ-G50, DNBSEQ-G400 FAST}	Metagenome and genome	S E Q U E N C I N G
R1 fastq filename	Name of the fastq forward file. "Accepted values / validation" columns: free text BUT the file name must end by "_r1.fastq.gz"	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	

ABRomics metadata referential

Sample Strain Sequencing

ABRomics metadata specifications

Field name	Description/guidelines for ABRomics users	ABRomics status	Type	Accepted values / validation	Additional comments	Metadata type
R2 fastq filename	<i>Name of the fastq reverse file.</i> <i>"Accepted values / validation" column: free text BUT the file name must end by "_r2.fastq.gz"</i>	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	G
Sequencing partner	<i>The name of the agency that did the sequencing.</i>	mandatory	string	free text	Metagenome and genome	